

Reproducibility Study - FANG: Leveraging Social Context for Fake News Detection Using Graph Representation

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Abstract

We reproduce and examine the experiments conducted in the paper "FANG: Leveraging Social Context for Fake News Detection Using Graph Representation". Differences between the memory capacity of our GPU and the one available to the authors lead to various out-of-memory errors when using the released code. This is due to inefficient memory usage during validation and testing, as the data is not processed in batches. We also uncover potential memory leaks. Our reproduced experiments yield in some cases strongly divergent results in model performance, measured using AUC. We deem the information provided by the authors regarding their experimental setup and its parameters as being insufficient for exact reproduction and validation of the paper's claimed results. Furthermore, we examine and critique the author's train-validation-test partition strategy and lack of statistical measurements over multiple experiment runs. Ultimately, we suggest improvements to remove the discussed shortcomings of the experiment design and improve the paper's reproducibility.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Social networks**; • **Computer systems organization** → **Neural networks**; • **Theory of computation** → *Semi-supervised learning*; • **Computing methodologies** → *Natural language processing*.

Keywords: Disinformation, Fake News, Social Networks, Graph Neural Networks, Representation Learning, Reproducibility Study, Experiment Design, Experimental Setup

1 Introduction

In this publication we describe our attempt to reproduce the results of the paper titled "FANG: Leveraging Social Context for Fake News Detection Using Graph Representation" [8], written by Van-Hoang Nguyen, Kazunari Sugiyama, Preslav Nakov and Min-Yen Kan. FANG stands for **F**actual **N**ews **G**raph and is a novel graphical social context representation and learning framework for fake news detection. The authors made their dataset and code available

in a GitHub repository¹. We forked² this repository and extended it with two notebooks containing the code used to obtain certain insights that will be mentioned in this work, as well as the code and data to recreate the plots in Figures 3 and 4.

We first give a brief summary of the paper's contents to provide the necessary context (Section 2). Secondly, we examine the paper's experimental setup in detail (Section 3). Thirdly, we discuss our reproduction efforts, present the obtained results and compare them to those found in the paper (Section 4). Finally, we critique the paper's experimental setup and offer suggestions on how to improve it (Section 5).

2 FANG - Paper Summary

2.1 Topic

With the rise of social media we also saw a significant outbreak in the emergence of disinformation bubbles commonly referred to as "fake news", which are increasingly leading to disturbances in social behavior and overall public rationality. Over the years many media sites and platforms such as Facebook, news papers, news websites or other sources of news made various efforts in combating this phenomenon, using different methods, such as user reporting, manual fact-checking and content moderation. These methods can achieve high accuracy but require considerable human effort. Lately, research has shown distinctive engagement patterns between real and fake news [2, 7]. Fake news tends to show high engagement shortly after its publication with verbatim re-circulations and negative sentiment. After this short time window has passed, the stance distribution stabilizes very rapidly and finally ends in virtually no support. On the contrary, real news shows moderate engagement, as well as a quickly stabilizing and overall more neutral sentiment.

2.2 Related Work

Due to the nature of the problem presented, the latest research shows that models using network representations are

¹<https://github.com/nguyenvanhoang7398/FANG>

²<https://github.com/d-vesely/FANG>

outperforming Euclidean-based methods [6, 9]. These graphical network representations, as seen in Figure 1, are better in modeling the heterogeneous entities and their varying dependencies, leading to more accurate data and subsequently more accurate prediction models. Some of the reasons for that are that in contrast to previous approaches, graphical representations also capture the user’s interactions, such as who they follow on social media, which topics they engage with, as well as what their stance is on said topics. Moreover, node variables can reinforce each other via edge interactions. Because Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) [3] have

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the social context. Users are connected via friend- or followership (yellow edges). Users express stances on news articles (dotted edges), which are published by news sources (red edges). News sources can cite other sources (blue edge).

limitations, such as a substantial memory footprint due to storing the entire adjacency matrix, as well as their limited adaptability to heterogeneous data, the authors decided to build their work on GraphSage [1]. According to the authors, it performs well as a framework for representation learning with unsupervised node proximity loss, even in a setting with minimal supervision.

2.3 Social Context Graph

As shown in Figure 1, the social context graph is defined as:

- News articles: $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_i\}$, where each a_i is modeled as a feature vector x_a .
- News sources: $S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_j\}$, where each s_i has published at least one article in A and is modeled as a feature vector x_s .
- Social users: $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_k\}$, where each u_k has engaged in spreading an article in A or is connected with another user, and is modeled as a feature vector x_u .
- Interactions: $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_l\}$, where each $e_l = \{v_1, v_2, t, x_e\}$ of type x_e is modeled as a relation between two entities $v_1, v_2 \in A \cup S \cup U$, e.g. an article and a user, at time t (t can also be absent in some cases).

Table 3 in the FANG paper summarizes the characteristics of different types of interactions. Since recent work [9] has established the significance of temporality, the authors are using it in their stance interaction data as well.

Finally, the authors define their final problem statement as follows: Given a social context $G = (A, S, U, E)$ constructed from news articles A , news sources S , social users U , and social engagements E , fake news detection is the binary classification task to predict whether a news article $a \in A$ is fake or real, meaning $F_C : a \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, where $F_C(a) = 0$ denotes a fake article and $F_C(a) = 1$ a real article. The authors describe the construction of the social context graph and their thoughts that went into it. Here a few noteworthy details:

- For news articles $a \in A$ the authors used unsupervised textual representation.
- For characterizing news sources $s \in S$ the authors focused on the textual content of their websites.
- For social users $u \in U$, information was gathered from their profile’s text description.
- For each of the three representations noted above, TF.IDF vectors were used [10].
- Each pair of social actors has an edge defining an interaction type. This type can be one of (a) Followship, i.e. u_i follows u_j on social media, (b) Citation, i.e. the homepage of s_i contains a hyperlink to s_j , (c) Publication, i.e. a_i was published by s_j , and (d) Stance, i.e. u_i has expressed a stance towards a_j , the nature of which (e.g. supportive stance, denial stance, etc.) is to be determined via stance detection.
- For time-sensitive interactions, i.e. stance expression and article publication, a timestamp relative to the article’s earliest publication was added.
- For stance detection, the authors decided to create their own dataset containing 2527 pairs of labeled source-target sentence pairs from 31 news sources on which they trained their own stance classifier. In the end, they fine-tuned the pertained RoBERTa [5] model on their dataset.

2.4 Factual News Graph (FANG) Framework

2.4.1 Representation Learning.

Figure 2 shows an overview of the FANG framework. FANG optimizes for fake news detection while also learning generalizable representations for the social entities using three concurrent losses: unsupervised proximity loss, self-supervised stance-loss and supervised fake news detection loss. The authors chose GraphSage as their node encoding function, as it allows the use of auxiliary node features as well, while other models only consider the graph neighbourhood structure. News nodes were enriched with user engagement temporality, which was demonstrated to be distinctive for fake news. Therefore the aggregating model needs to be time-sensitive.

Figure 2. Overview of the FANG Framework. Image source: [8].

Because bidirectional LSTMs can capture long-term dependencies, this architecture was chosen. The authors also incorporated an attention mechanism to focus on essential engagement during encoding.

2.4.2 Unsupervised Proximity Loss.

The so called echo chamber phenomenon describes the tendency of social entities to fortify their own beliefs and narratives, by interacting solely with entities who agree, while ignoring or not even perceiving those who do not. This inspired the authors to formulate the hypothesis that closely connected social entities will often display similar behaviour. By the same token, loosely-connected social entities will often behave very differently, thus polarizing social entities. Additionally, as most of the interactions are either between (a) sources and news or (b) between news, the authors split the social context graph into a news-source- and a user-sub-graph.

2.4.3 Self-Supervised Stance Loss.

Moreover, the stance classification is optimized using a stance-loss based on the principle for user-news interactions that the representations of a user and an article should be similar, if the user expresses a stance towards said news article.

2.4.4 Supervised Fake News Loss.

Finally, the authors optimize the detection of fake news using a supervised loss. Hereby a concatenation of an article’s representation and the structural representation of its source is fed into a fully connected layer.

In the end, all the described losses are combined to a total loss: $L_{total} = L_{prox} + L_{stance} + L_{news}$. For much more detailed explanations and formulas, please refer to the FANG paper.

3 Experimental Setup

The authors tested their model on a Twitter dataset collected by related work [4, 7, 11], which they enhanced with additional data they collected. The final dataset contained 448 fake and 606 real news articles (1054 in total) from 442 sources, with a total of 54461 engaged users. As already mentioned, this dataset was made available by the authors via a GitHub repository (see Section 1).

In the paper, the ability of FANG to detect fake news is compared against the following three other baselines (for details on each of these models refer to the cited sources):

- A Support Vector Machine used on feature vectors constructed from the news content, i.e. a content-only model that disregards contextual features.
- *Capture, Score and Integrate* (CSI), a Euclidean model [9].
- The Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) graph learning framework [3].

Furthermore, temporal-insensitive variants of both the CSI and FANG models were used in the comparison as well, with the purpose of confirming the hypothesized importance of modeling temporality (see Section 2.4.1).

The authors use the area under the Receiver Operating Characteristics curve (AUC) as a performance benchmark to evaluate and compare the above mentioned models. In the provided code AUC is used for model evaluation as well, which happens after each epoch per default. While accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score (using macro-averages for the latter three metrics) are computed both after each epoch and for the best model, none of these results are listed in the paper.

In order to test how well FANG operates with limited training data, the authors also conducted additional experiments with training set sizes of 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 90% of the data. The temporal sensitive CSI and the GCN models are used as reference models in these experiments, as well as a variant of the FANG model without stance loss (see Section 2.4.3). Although this is not explicitly mentioned, it can be derived from the results in the paper’s Tables 7 and 8 that the training data used in the overall model comparison is comprised of the same 90% as in Table 8 comparing results for varying sizes of training data, since the listed AUC scores are equivalent.

For the purpose of clarity, we copy the results from the paper and list them in Table 1. The authors refer to these results as "macroscopic results". While the term "macroscopic" certainly hints to the possibility that these measurements were not the result of single experiments and are rather averages computed over multiple runs, it is to be highlighted that the exact experimental setup remains unclear. Neither is it stated that each model was trained multiple times, nor that the reported measurements are averages. Variances or

standard deviations, which would be notable measurements in the case of repeated experiments, are also not mentioned.

When it comes to data partitioning, the authors split into training, testing and validation sets. For the latter dataset the terminology is mixed in the code, as it is also referred to as "dev"(-elopment) set in some cases. Partitioning does not occur during run-time via random sampling, instead, the authors provide JSON-files of pre-partitioned data. One file for each of the used training set sizes, as described earlier (these files are located in the repository directory `data/news_graph/train_test_xx.json`, where `xx` is the training set percentage, e.g. 10). Interestingly, all provided partitions contain 1037 nodes, while the complete dataset is comprised of 1054 news articles, as mentioned above. Our analysis shows that on the one hand, there are 18 articles of class "real" in the dataset that are not included in any of the partitions. And on the other hand, there is one node in all partitions, whose ID does not exist in the dataset, and is thus ignored by the code. Usually, the actual training set size in the provided partitions is a few nodes above the denoted percentages, e.g. 938 out of 1037, as opposed to $1037 \cdot 0.9 = 933.3$. For each partition, the remaining nodes that are not part of the training set are all divided up into the validation and test sets. These two sets are in all cases of either equal or almost equal size, with the validation set being larger by 2 or 3 nodes. We analyzed the connections between the sets in the five partitions, to check whether each partition was randomly generated or not. We visualized the results of said analysis using a Sankey diagram (see Figure 3), where each of the five partitions and its training (blue), test (green) and validation (purple) sets are aligned vertically and of correct relative size. We gain the following insights:

- With increasing training percentages, the set of training nodes is extended, as opposed to being sampled anew. This is clearly visible when tracking the connections between the training set blocks, from the rightmost 10% to the leftmost 90%. All outgoing lines always lead into the training set of the next higher partition. This effectively means that 10% of the data are always part of a training set in each partition.
- The same is the case for the test set, with increasing test set size, the test set is also not re-sampled, just extended. This can be seen by tracking the connections between test sets in the other direction, from the leftmost, smallest test set, to the right. Analogously, 10% of the data are always part of a test set in each partition.
- With decreasing training or test set sizes, the remaining data are transferred into the validation sets of the next partition. Only for the 90%-partition this is not the case, since some of the training data is transferred to the test set in the 70%-partition.

Training, Testing and Validation Sets used in FANG

Figure 3. Relative sizes of training (blue), validation (purple) and testing (green) datasets for each training percentage partition (90%, 70%, 50%, 30% and 10% of the data, from left to right). Connections indicate the shared data between the individual partitions.

It is not explicitly mentioned whether these five provided partitions are exactly those that were used to obtain the results presented in the paper or not. However, these partitions are used by default in the code, depending on the percentage specified by the user. There is a mechanism in the code which uses *scikit-learn*'s `train_test_split()` function to partition the data, but this can only be activated and customized in terms of training percentages by altering the code directly, as opposed to using the provided arguments.

Additionally, the number of training epochs that the authors ran when evaluating the FANG model's performance is not discussed. However, in the published code, that number is set to 30 by default, but it can also be changed with a corresponding argument, without the need of altering the code.

The authors allow users to explicitly set a seed in the training configuration file (located at `training/configs.py`), in order to ensure reproducibility in the face of randomness. There is a default value for the seed, but the specific value used for the experiments is not stated. Furthermore, our examination of the code showed that the seed variable is dead code, i.e. not propagated or used in any other module.

4 Reproduced Results

We reran the FANG training for both the complete model and the model without stance loss, with all of the training set size percentages used by the authors. We assumed that the default values set in the code, i.e. the number of epochs, the provided train-test-validation splits in JSON-format, the batch size, etc., were the ones used in the author's experiments. Of course, since an explicit seed is not being set (see Section 3), determinacy is not guaranteed.

According to the README in the FANG GitHub repository, the authors ran their experiments on a Titan RTX GPU with 24220MiB of total memory. Since this specific hardware was not available to us, we used a GeForce GTX 1080 with

Table 1. Summary of experiment results listed in the FANG paper. Empty cells indicate that no result was reported for that setting.

System	AUC score at training percentage				
	10%	30%	50%	70%	90%
Feat. SVM					0.5525
CSI(-t)					0.6678
CSI	0.6363	0.6714	0.6700	0.6887	0.6911
GCN	0.5918	0.6445	0.6797	0.6642	0.7064
FANG(-t)					0.7179
FANG(-s)	0.6396	0.6708	0.6773	0.7090	0.7411
FANG	0.6683	0.7036	0.7166	0.7232	0.7518

8118MiB of total memory. While training with a training set size of 90% or 70% worked, this difference in available GPU memory was causing issues for the smaller training partitions due to the much larger validation and test sets, as described in Section 3. Concretely, CUDA out-of-memory run-time errors occurred during the validation/testing of a completed epoch (by default, this happens after every epoch), due to an attempted allocation of more memory than was available. Reducing the batch size and/or the number of hidden layers had no effect. Closer examination showed that for validation and testing, the data is not divided into mini-batches, instead it is processed as a single batch. The 70% partition, which has a validation and test set of 156 and 154 nodes respectively, utilized almost all memory capacities

We attempted to build a crude batching mechanism, by simply passing the nodes in smaller subsets to the evaluation function. Nonetheless, this caused the same errors in a nondeterministic pattern, meaning that the error occurred at various stages, sometimes during validation, other times during testing and also with different batches. This indicates memory leaks.

Running the training on the CPU mitigated this problem, since system memory is being used instead of the limited GPU memory. This, of course, has the disadvantage of a significantly prolonged runtime. We therefore chose to adapt the partitions and reduce the validation/test sizes, by copying the sets from the 70%-partition. As can be seen from Figure 3, none of the nodes in the validation/test sets in the 70%-partition are used in the training sets of any other partition with smaller training set sizes. However, while this worked fine with the complete model, it inexplicably again led to CUDA out-of-memory errors when training the model without stance loss. We therefore used the validation/test sets from the 90%-partition (which also do not contain nodes that are used in training).

Table 2 lists our reproduced results, and a plot with both the paper’s AUC scores and our own results is shown in Figure 4.

Table 2. Reproduced AUC scores of FANG and the model’s version without stance loss for varying training set sizes.

System	AUC score at training percentage				
	10%	30%	50%	70%	90%
FANG(-s)	0.7946	0.8196	0.7518	0.7152	0.8536
FANG	0.6503	0.7327	0.7216	0.7308	0.8196

Figure 4. The results from the paper (red and blue), our own experiment results for the default FANG model (green) and the FANG model without stance loss (purple) at the same training percentages used in the paper and a result achieved by our own training-validation-test partition (orange).

The results obtained for the training sizes of 90% and 70%, using the partition files provided by the authors, do not match with the scores listed in the paper. While the scores for the 70%-partition are quite similar, our scores for the 90%-partition improved by 9.02% and by 15.18% for FANG and FANG(-s) respectively. In fact, the model without stance loss outperforms the complete model with an AUC score improvement of 4.15%. For the 10%-, 30%- and 50%-partitions, we see strongly diverging results for the two model variants. As already mentioned, for the model without stance loss, we used the validation and test sets from the 90%-partition and for the complete model we used those from the 70%-partition. The former seems to contain favorable nodes, as we achieved very high scores, even for the training set size of only 10%. The AUC score of the model without stance loss, trained with 10% of the data, was 24.23% better than the score reported in the paper. When trained with 30% of the data, it achieved the same AUC score as the complete model with a training set size of 90%.

Finally, we also created our own partition file with set sizes equal to those used in the provided 90%-partition, i.e. 938 training nodes, 51 validation nodes and 48 test nodes.

The intersection between our test set and the test set from the 90%-partition contained only a single node. The FANG model using the new partition file achieved an AUC score of 0.6527. As can be seen from Figure 4, this is close to being the worst score obtained in our experiments. In comparison to when the original 90%-partition was used, the AUC score dropped by more than 20%. This might indicate that FANG generalizes poorly.

5 Critique & Suggestions

The information provided by the authors regarding parameter settings, as well as the train-validation-test partitions used, is not sufficient to reproduce the results presented in the paper.

The way the authors partition their data into training, validation and test sets is not ideal from our point of view. Since the AUC scores computed on the test sets are used for comparison against the baselines, as well as for comparison of the FANG model variants, its size and contents should be equal for all evaluations. Otherwise, it can not be determined whether an increased AUC score was a consequence of a better model, or simply due to one test set containing easily classifiable data, and another containing *additional* data that is much more difficult to classify. For instance, our reproduction efforts described in the previous section have shown that the test set from the 90%-partition seems to contain very favorable data, as models trained with a substantially reduced training set size still performed well.

We would recommend a data partitioning process, where 5% of the data is sampled into a test set and put aside. The remaining 95% can then be split into training and validation sets and used in training. The test data should only be used for the final evaluation.

A larger test set might be a good idea as well, since 5% of the data is only ~50 nodes in this case. Of course, this is constrained by the task of using 90% of the data for training.

Since k-fold cross-validation is not an option, as it does not allow for precisely testing the specific training set sizes, experiments should be repeated multiple times with different partitions, ideally recording the specific random seed used for each experiment run. As already mentioned in Section 3, it is unclear whether the authors did that or not. Nevertheless, insights about the model’s robustness that one would gain from statistical measurements over multiple experiment runs, such as variance, range, mean, median or quartiles, are not reported. Especially considering the partially very differing results obtained by us, these statistics would be very important to be able to better understand and compare the models.

6 Conclusion

Due to our GPU having approximately $\frac{1}{3}$ of the memory capacity of the one used by the authors, we had to adjust the

sizes of the test and validation sets for certain experiments, as no batching mechanism was built in. While we were able to rerun the experiments with the provided code, we did not obtain the exact measurements presented in the paper. Furthermore, we showed that the achieved scores vary highly, depending on the contents of the test and validation sets. We also examined the experimental setup employed by the authors, discussed its shortcomings, as well as suggested changes that would improve the validity of the presented results.

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